

NOTES

Reduction of Potassium Persulphate by Aqueous Hydrogen Sulphide and N-sulphurous Acid

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The present attempt is in continuation of the earlier work on oxidation reduction undertaken in this laboratory¹⁻⁸.

Fresh samples of aqueous hydrogen sulphide (*loc. cit.*) and N-sulphurous acid (*loc. cit.*) were prepared when required as usual and potassium persulphate used was always of A. R. quality.

The reaction was studied with 10, 30, 50 and 70 ml. of freshly prepared aqueous hydrogen sulphide and then with hydrogen sulphide gas. The end products and also the unreacted potassium persulphate⁹, if any, were estimated and recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Reduction of potassium persulphate by aqueous hydrogen sulphide (in aqueous solution)

Potassium persulphate taken = 0.5 g.

Expt. No.	H ₂ S-H ₂ O added (ml.)	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ reduced (%)	K ₂ SO ₄ observed (g.)	H ₂ SO ₄ observed (g)	S (free) if ppted.
1	10.0	22.16	0.0714	0.0386	Yes
		22.16	0.0714	0.0394	
		45.10	0.1454	0.0814	
2.	30.0	44.44	0.1429	0.0796	Yes
		58.52	0.1887	0.1065	
		58.52	0.1887	0.1052	
3.	50.0	79.92	0.2578	0.1438	Yes
		79.92	0.2578	0.1447	
		79.92	0.3223	0.1811	
4.	70.0	100.00	0.3223	0.1803	Yes
		Gas bubbled in excess			
5.					

1. K. Lal, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 934.
2. K. Lal and G. Singh, *-ibid-*, 1955, **32**, 58.
3. Idem *-ibid-* 1954, 1955, **31**, 410; **32**, 65; 1955, **32**, 547.
4. K. Lal and C. Mehra, *-ibid-* 1956, **33**, 668, 1957, **34**, 131.
5. K. Lal, and S. S. Pahil, *-ibid-* 1959, **36**, 467.
6. K. Lal and R. L. Kaushik, *Res. Bull Panj. Univ.*, 1959, **10**, 257, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 181.
7. K. Lal and M. S. Sohal, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 162.
8. K. L. Jaura, et. al., *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 759.
9. F. S. Itton, "A systematic handbook of volumetric analysis" Butterworths Scientific Publications, London, 1955, p. 443.

The reaction was further studied in presence of excess of sodium bicarbonate enough to maintain the reaction medium always distinctly alkaline and the end products estimated and recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Reduction of potassium persulphate by aqueous hydrogen sulphide (in alkaline medium)

Potassium persulphate taken = 0.5 g.

Expt. No.	H ₂ S.H ₂ O added (ml)	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ reduced (%)	SO ₃ ²⁻ formed (g.)	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻ formed (g.)	SO ₄ ²⁻ observed (g.)	S(free) if ppted.	Polysulphides if present
1.	5.0	36.48	nil	traces	0.1288	yes	no
		36.74			0.1316		
2.	10.0	68.84	nil	0.0032	0.2430	yes	no
		68.84			0.0027		
3.	15.0	100.00	0.0020	0.0056	0.3548	yes	no
			0.0020	0.0056	0.3540		
4.	20.0	100.00	nil	0.0129	0.3560	yes	yes
				0.0129	0.3552		
5.	30.0	100.00	nil	0.0145	0.3550	yes	yes
				0.0145	0.3546		

The investigations were repeated with N-sulphurous acid similarly and the results recorded in Tables III and IV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Decomposition of persulphate in aqueous solution to free sulphuric acid and oxygen makes the reaction mixture acidic and oxidises hydrogen sulphide slowly to liberate free sulphur. Formation of dithionate is not possible since the sulphite ions are not available to react with the sulphur liberated (Table I).

In the alkaline medium the reaction mixture turns yellow due to the formation of polysulphides which slowly get oxidised by the unreacted persulphate to sulphur, thio-sulphate and sulphate when kept in dark. This trend continues till persulphate is completely acted upon and then the polysulphides remain unattacked in the solution. Traces of sulphite have been detected only when both, persulphate and hydrogen sulphide, happen

to be absent in the reaction mixture (Expt. 3, Table II). The overall mechanism of the

TABLE III

*Reduction of potassium persulphate by N-sulphurous acid
(in aqueous solution)*

Potassium persulphate taken = 0.5 g.

Expt. No.	N-H ₂ SO ₃ added (ml.)	Time allowed to complete reaction (days)	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ reduced (%)	K ₂ SO ₄ observed (g.)	H ₂ SO ₄ due to persulphate decomposition (g.)	H ₂ SO ₄ due to oxidation (g.)	H ₂ S ₂ O ₆ formed (g.)
			30.38	0.0979	0.0551	0.0523	0.0083
1	2.0	2	29.90	0.0964	0.0542	0.0542	0.008C
2.	5.0	4	52.98	0.1708	0.0961	0.0877	0.0142
			54.18	0.1747	0.093	0.0869	0.0146
3.	10.0	10	89.98	0.2899	0.1632	0.1520	0.0243
			90.22	9.2909	0.1633	0.1510	0.0249
4.	15.0	12	100.00	0.3223	0.1814	0.1661	0.0278
				0.3223	0.1814	0.1668	0.0271

reaction may be represented as :

Increase in the thiosulphate content corresponding to the increasing additions of hydrogen sulphide (Table II) supports the proposed mechanism. This also suggests that formation of sulphite starts from early stages of the reaction although it is detected much later. Both free sulphur and sulphite continue to be produced as long as persulphate is available in the reaction mixture and their slow interaction continues till one of the reactants is completely acted upon.

Oxidation of sulphurous acid by persulphate (Table III) yields sulphate, dithionate and free sulphuric acid, the latter being formed partly by the direct oxidation of sulphurous acid also. The medium of reaction being always acidic and free sulphur absent the formation of thiosulphate, tetrathionate and other higher thionates is completely ruled out. Formation of dithionate, however, may be regarded through sulphite as proposed by Bassett and Henry¹⁰ as :

Almost constant ratio between the dithionate and the sulphate contents throughout the reaction suggests that their formations are independent of the concentrations of the reactants.

Reaction in the alkaline medium is fast but sulphate is the only product. Free sulphur being absent formation of thionates is impossible (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Reduction of potassium persulphate by N-sulphurous acid (in alkaline medium)

Potassium persulphate taken : 1.0 g.

Expt. No.	NH ₂ SO ₃ added (ml.)	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ reduced (%)	SO ₄ ²⁻ due to persulphate decomp. (g)	SO ₄ ²⁻ due to oxidation (g)
1	3.00	{ 34.46 34.46	{ 0.2450 0.2450	{ 0.1217 0.1230
2.	5.0	{ 57.75 57.88	{ 0.4105 0.4112	{ 0.2054 0.2062
3.	7.0	{ 81.17 81.04	{ 0.5769 0.5756	{ 0.2879 0.2872
4.	15.0	100.00	{ 0.7108 0.7108	{ 0.3602 0.3654

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